

Briefly describe how macroeconomic policy has helped or hurt the economy of the Eurozone since the world financial crisis and recession 2008-09.

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Introduction

The world economy in 2008-09 confronted its most downright financial shock that is likely to have considerable implications for the design and operation of economic institutions. Although national financial crises occur relatively periodically, global financial crises are exceptionally rare, this being only the third such global crisis since the Long Depression of 1873-79¹. Over the past periods, most of the crises have had their roots in developing and emerging countries, often ensuing from abrupt reversals in capital flows, and from loose domestic monetary and fiscal policies. In contrast, the 2008-09 global financial crisis has had its roots in the US following the bankruptcy of Lehman Brothers in September 2008 as a result of the sustained rise in asset prices, particularly house prices, on the back of excessively accommodative monetary policy and lax lending standards during 2002-2006 coupled with financial innovations that resulted in a large rise in mortgage credit to households, particularly low credit quality households². This made the economic and financial environment very difficult for the world economy, the global financial system and for central banks³. While within the Eurozone the crisis does not make it to the headlines of the media anymore, except for Greece, it is still in full force.

As the global financial catastrophe unravelled, the urgency to intervene in order to avoid a catastrophic collapse of the financial markets and real economy consisted of three main interventions: 1) bailouts and injections of money into the financial system to keep credit flowing; 2) cutting interest rates to stimulate borrowing and investment; and 3) extra fiscal spending to shore up aggregate demand⁴. These measures sought to prevent further economic deterioration and ultimately keep workers in jobs where possible and help create new jobs to provide opportunities for the unemployed. This paper summarizes how economies around the Eurozone have been affected by various macroeconomic policy interventions. This task is undertaken in two folds, first, the paper provides a summary of the policy responses of Eurozone governments to the global financial crisis that took hold in 2007 and finally it provides concluding remarks.

1. Monetary and financial policy

a) Interest rate reductions

The first important factor in the run-up to the crisis was the remarkable decline in short-term interest rates. This led to a situation in which Taylor rules⁵ – that model the interest rate as a function of the deviation from targeted inflation and the output gap – proved successful in empirically describing the behaviour of central banks. Against the low inflation background, policy rates were thus left at very low levels and below the level implied by the Taylor rule.

b) Deposit guarantee schemes

During the recent crisis, as global capital markets froze, the availability of bank financing for trade declined and where available its costs increased considerably. This increasing difficulty in obtaining trade

¹ 'Numerous Explanations for the 1873 Crisis Have Been Put Forth but the US and European Demonetization of Silver Is Foremost.'

² Andrew Haldane, 'Why Banks Failed The Stress Test?', *Bank of England*, 2009.

³ G Lobal F Inancial and others, 'Global Financial Crisis : Causes , Impact , Policy Responses and Lessons', *Stanford Center for International Development*, 407, 2009, 40.

⁴ Paul Ramskogler, 'Tracing the Origins', *OECD Journal: Financial Market Trends*, 2014 (2015), 17.

⁵ John Taylor, 'The Financial Crisis and the Policy Responses: An Empirical Analysis of What Went Wrong', *National Bureau of Economic Research*, Working Paper 14631, 2009.

finance was a contributing factor explaining the large declines in trade during the crisis. ⁶In addition, as uncertainty increased during the crisis, exporters became less willing to give importers the goods on credit and increasingly demanded bank financing (i.e., a letter of credit) just as the availability of this financing was declining. In addition, since significant concerns developed about the solvency of the banking systems in some economies such as Kazakhstan and Ukraine, exporters or even foreign government export-promotion agencies began to question the reliability of the banks providing the letters of credit⁷.

2. Exchange rate/capital account

a) Exchange rate depreciations

The crisis resulted in significant depreciations in the EEE currencies versus the not only the US dollar but even the euro which declined significantly versus the dollar as well. Generally most of the currencies of the transition economies have declined by about 20 per cent relative to the US dollar⁸. This provided some boost in competitiveness for the region but given that foreign currency loans were significant in much of the region this worsened the debt situation of those borrowers. In fact, the large “balance sheet” impact of a depreciation on the borrowers with foreign-currency denominated debt was the most important factor that limited the ability of European governments to adjust to the trade shock with a depreciation. The two countries in Europe that escaped from having a recession during this crisis were Poland and Albania. Both countries allowed their currencies to depreciate during the worst phase of the crisis. The Polish zloty was allowed to depreciate by 32 per cent (versus the US\$) from its peak in early 2008 while the Albanian lek was allowed to depreciate 12 per cent (on a monthly average basis) between early 2008 and March of 2010. This allowed both export and import competing firms in these economies to remain competitive⁹.

Summary and Conclusions

Common currency areas reduce the degree of flexibility in case of a need for adjustment caused by an asymmetric shock: whereas Iceland was able to achieve a 25% fall in wages relative to the Eurozone with a single devaluation, Spain—with a similar problem of overvaluation—was unable to do so¹⁰. In the case of an Open Currency Area, however, a highly unequal economic performance between sub-regions caused by an exogenous shock could be compensated by strong geographical labour mobility, highly flexible labour markets or a common system of risk-sharing.

⁶ Andreas Nölke, ‘Economic Causes of the Eurozone Crisis : The Analytical Contribution of Comparative Capitalism’, *Socio-Economic Review*, 14.1 (2016), 141–61 <<https://doi.org/10.1093/ser/mwv031>>.

⁷ Robert C Shelburne, ‘THE GLOBAL FINANCIAL CRISIS AND ITS IMPACT ON TRADE : THE WORLD AND THE EUROPEAN EMERGING ECONOMIES’, *UNITED NATIONS ECONOMIC COMMISSION FOR EUROPE*, 2010, 30.

⁸ Sebastian Dullien, Detlef J Kotte, and Jan Priewe, *The FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC CRISIS OF 2008-2009 AND DEVELOPING COUNTRIES* (New York and Geneva: UNCTAD, 2010).

⁹ Andrew K Rose and others, ‘Cross-Country Causes and Consequences of the 2008 Crisis : Early Warning Early Warning’, *Federal Reserve Bank of San Francisco.*, 2009, 55.

¹⁰ P. Krugman, ‘Revenge of the Optimum Currency Area’, *The New York Times*, 24 June 2012.